

MUNICIPAL AWARENESS AS A TOOL FOR ENHANCING CITIZEN SATISFACTION IN MUNICIPAL COUNCILS OF MALAYSIA

Muhammad Umar Bello^{1,2*},

David Martin Daud Juani¹,

Rozilah Kasim²

¹Department of Real Estate Management,
Faculty of Technology Management and Business,
UTHM, Parit Raja, Malaysia

²Department of Estate Management and Valuation,
Faculty of Environmental Technology,
ATBU, Bauchi, Nigeria

Abstract:

This research study critically analysed the existing literatures on municipal awareness relevancy of LAs service delivery for the purpose of enhancing citizen satisfaction. The purpose of the study is the investigation of citizen satisfaction level of municipal services; analysis of the existing literatures on relationship between municipal awareness and citizen satisfaction. The Material and methods were carried out using secondary data and were meticulously and critically analysed to come up with reliable results. The study shows the relevancy of the public awareness, citizen satisfaction and municipal council performance in Malaysia. It is evidence in the research that citizen consent is importance before municipal services should be provided in the local community. The research study highlighted many discrepancies in many literatures related to the existing research study, evidence based analysis were carried out to buttress importance and significance of the related study to the research work. The literatures were reviewed to ascertain the current happening in the area of local government service delivery. The study shows that many municipal councils in Malaysia provide adequate and satisfactory services to their citizens'. The study also revealed that municipal council plays important role on citizen awareness of municipal service delivery. The study concludes that municipal service delivery can be enhanced through citizen awareness campaign, to sensitize the local community on various

¹ Correspondence: email mubello78@gmail.com

aspects of service delivery including maintenance of the facilities provided. The study also concludes that LAs lack of awareness section affects their performance in service delivery process. The study recommends that LAs need to consults the citizen for their needs and wants; awareness campaign need to be regularly carried out to maintain cordial relationship between LAs and their citizen; it is also recommended that municipal services should be delivered the needed services by the local inhabitants' after duly consultation.

Keywords: municipal awareness, citizen satisfaction, municipal council, local government

1. Introduction

Citizen lack of awareness of the administration of local government is the major hindrance to the development of the local government areas and the inhabitants (Callahan, 2002; Ebdon, 2002; Unegbu, 2013). Responsiveness of citizen towards the local authorities' service delivery are determined by the level of citizen awareness (Almarshad, 2011; Barnes, 1999; Darison, 2011; Sandford, 2016), citizen satisfaction in Malaysian public sector were given attention especially in local authorities' (Khalid, 2010), local authorities inhabitants need and wants are attended unsatisfactorily Siddiquee, (2006) and Dewulf and van Meel, (2002). Awareness of citizen on the outcome of local authorities' performance outcome may foster cordial understanding.

Lack of government commitment towards satisfying local government inhabitants necessitated this study. Creation and establishment of required information can empower local authority with benefits of citizen compliance of their regulations (Almarshad, 2015; Zamzami, 2004) and (Borins, 2012; Wihlman, 2014), against this background awareness of citizen on the performance of local authorities in many countries of the world are based on the seriousness of the government official to enlighten their citizens. Thus, one of the exceptional issues of local authority in Malaysia is that there is no adequate information channel to the citizens. Furthermore, many interests of the citizens are not fully represented in the higher level of decision making of the local councils. In some cases, there is strong political interference in local authorities that affects their actions and decisions.

Many researches has shown that there are various factors impart in creating citizen awareness, satisfaction and sense of belongingness toward brands of any kind but sometimes customers themselves are unaware of the reasons for the brand preferences (Hanif, Muzammil. and Sehrish, 2010). In the contemporary time the only

constant agent is change. LAs positive change towards advancement of service delivery and information dissemination among the inhabitants enhance the LAs position in terms of provisioning of municipal services. Ofoeze, (1997) and (2003) assertion is that local government areas are created to solve rural developmental problems and to provide services at satisfactory level. Services such as street sweeping, grass cutting, parking space provisioning etc. are required to be provided and maintained by both the LAs and the citizens' Hilgers & Ihl, (2010) and (Group, 2011), With the marvelous increase in population connected a municipality (Almarshad, 2015), LAs are the bedrock of development of local people and monitoring wing of social justice (Amin & Isa, 2008; Andrews, Boyne, Law, & Walker, 2005; Antuono, Meeks, Miller, & Watchou, 2006; Khalid, 2010; Unegbu, 2013).

2. Literatures Review

There are limited literatures on citizen awareness for enhancing citizen satisfaction of municipal service delivery. This study tries to highlight the important of citizen awareness in local government service delivery.

2.1 Citizen Awareness

Citizen awareness is very important concepts because it involved understanding and participation of citizen (Almarshad, 2015; Sureshchandar, & Chandreskharan, 2002). Citizen awareness have been characterized as having ties to the need and wants to the developmental services within their local territory (Bache, 2013; Milinthajinda, 1999; Wang & Shieh, 2006). Citizen were concerned about their local community development and this give them a deep awareness of local government administration appreciation for services needed, and sense of responsibility and participation as stakeholder (Mccann, Elizabeth & Shannon, Donna, & Young, 1997). The awareness of this concept was expressed by mobilizations in favour of municipal service development (Mccann, Elizabeth, & Shannon *et al.*, 1997; Sayers, 2006). Meanwhile, the councils of local government, civil society organizations, political parties [and] donor agencies all participate in the preparation of village/district profiles, preparation of Periodic Plans, and determination of development priorities, an assessment of the people's present information literacy capabilities is crucial (Aagesen, 2012; Abe, Monisola, & State, 2014; Abid, 2004; UNESCO, 2006).

2.1.1 Political Awareness

Political awareness are means of citizen understanding of political affairs of their locality, the headship of local government was charge to create resources of public enlightenment towards the municipal process of service delivery (Adeyemi, 2013; Agba, Akwara, & Idu, 2013; Aijaz, 2007; Filipe, Álvaro, Joaquim, Manuel, 2016). Management of local government expressively should be keen in obliging any policy that will improve the process of municipal service delivery (Kernaghan, 2015; Khalid, 2010). Creation of mechanism to enlighten the inhabitants on issues related to their life and wellbeing is the main function of local government officials. Political awareness by the nationals' and peoples enable them understand their condition and direction of the local council. Criticisms and grievances' can be channelled properly to the local government (Blaug, Horner, & Lekhi, 2006; Shafie, 2013). Many scholars linked citizens' satisfaction with the awareness of the local communities on the services delivered and their expectations on the performance of the local government (Mishler & Rose, 2001; Newton, 2001; Putnam, 1993; Stoner-Weiss, 1997).

2.1.2 Maintenance Awareness

The bounteousness of 21st century industrial tycoons bestowed many of our finest cities with far-reaching formal and semi-formal facilities and uncountable parks, all of which require on-going maintenance (Aliyu & Abdu, 2015; Reynolds et al., 2011). Similar-Facilities provided by the local council need to be preserved and maintained by both the producers and the users (Lind & Muyingo, 2012; Reynolds et al., 2011), before this can be done properly mutual understanding must be sustained between the providers and the users. Municipal branding and the development of local community plays a significant role in urban development (Jusoh, 2009). Nevertheless, in particular these services also have a reverse side-effect in regard to urban sustainability in the absence of users' awareness.

2.2 Citizen Satisfaction

Around 1989 Sweden became the first country in the world to established standardized cross company and cross industry methodology of measuring customer satisfaction and customer loyalty (Sajid, 2013). This general and national measurement gadget for customer satisfaction and customer loyalty is called the Swedish Customer Satisfaction Barometer (SCSB). Satisfaction of municipal services is one of the major evaluation of LAs service delivery performance (Mohammad Anwer, Vatcharaporn, Mariam, Maria, 2016). LAs performance must commiserate with citizen satisfaction of municipal services provisioned by local council, satisfaction of citizenry should be main target of

local government officials. To makes a meaningful development within the demarcation of local council, the needs and wants of the inhabitants' fulfilment represents the activeness of the local councils. In Malaysia the position of local councils allow them to take the responsibility of providing services to the local community (Mansor & Razali, 2010; Rozilah, Musa, Bala, 2011; Samsudin, Haron, & Bakar, 2012; Subhan, Ghani, & Joarder, 2014). If the municipal services delivered by the local councils are perceived as poor, the future of good governance and professional images of this local councils will be at stake (Samsudin et al., 2012). Malaysian federal government set a side large sum of money for local community development services (Mohamed, Izzati, Bachok, & Zin Mohamed, 2015).

Table 1: Evidence Based Analysis Of Related Literatures On The Study

No	Author & Date	Title	Findings	Observation
1	Almarshad, (2015)	Municipal Awareness and Citizen Satisfaction : The Case of Northern Borders in Saudi Arabia	The results of the study revealed positive relationship between municipal awareness and citizen satisfaction.	The study is failed to assess the level of citizen satisfaction of municipal services provided by the local government.
2	Mohamed <i>et al</i> , (2012)	An Assessment of Local Authority Performance in Delivering Their Services: Case Study of Ipoh City Council	Issue identified were the lack of transparency, delays in services, lack of customer service courtesy and unaccountable practices that obstructs governmental effectiveness and creates numerous complaints among public and respondents.	The study is did not give emphasis on customer chance to participates on service delivery.
3	Mansor, <i>et al</i> , (2010)	Customers ' Satisfaction towards Counter Service of Local Authority in Terengganu , Malaysia	Findings revealed that, there were significant relationships between the selected dimensions as to the main theme of the study.	The study is limited to counter service alone and did not treat other aspects of service delivery.
4	Donnelly, <i>et al</i> , (1995)	Measuring service quality in local government: the SERVQUAL approach.	Findings of the studies revealed that, service provider usually over- estimate service user expectation.	The research study is limited because it consider only the users' expectation not there attitude towards service provided.
5	Mokhlis, S., (2011)	Municipal Service Quality and Citizen Satisfaction in Southern Thailand	Findings of the study provide various important administrative implications for municipal councils by present them practical guidelines to improve quality services that would increase citizen satisfaction.	The research study is limited because is customers consent were not seek before service is provided.

Source: Authors' survey, 2016

The table 1 above shows different research on local government service delivery with different dimension of service delivery. The studies revealed different outcomes of the researches; study 1 revealed that there are a number of explicit uncertainties that affect service delivery, citizen satisfaction. Research 2,3,4 and 5 focused on citizen satisfaction of local government service delivery.

3. Material and Methods

Data used in this research paper were extracted from secondary sources of data which comprised of textbooks, articles, thesis and statutory documents. The data were critically reviewed to ascertain the current happening in the area of local government service delivery. It must be emphasised here that the method adopted for data collection in this study is a literature review analysis. Upon extracting data from the review, inferences will be drawn on municipal awareness for enhancing citizen satisfaction of municipal services in local government in Malaysia.

4. Result and Discussion

The result of the research study was revealed that municipal council in Malaysia provide adequate and satisfactory services to their citizens, but need additional efforts as it was evident in the work of (Kaliannan, Puteh, & Dorasamy, 2014; Mokhlis, 2011). The authenticity of this research work is verified thoroughly, and the results vindicated that similar research come to agree with the conclusion of the results of this research work in many respects. The work of (Almarshad, 2015) that indicate that awareness of citizen is integral part of process of assessing government performance, this also agree with the final result of this research work. Municipal services quality are determined by the quality of the inhabitants' life, the study of (Ireland, 2004) also agree with the finding of this research work. This particular study did not agree with the research of (Kugonza & Mukobi, 2015) that emphasised that community participation is only the key indicators for satisfactory service delivery.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This research work concluded that municipal services delivery can be enhance through citizen awareness campaign, to sensitise the local community on various aspects of service delivery including maintenance of the facilities provided. It is also concluding that LAs lack of awareness section affects their performance in service delivery. The

study recommended that LAs need to consult the citizen for their needs and wants; awareness campaign need to be regularly carried out to maintain cordial relationship between LAs and their citizen; it is also recommended that municipal services should be delivered after duly consultation with the local communities.

Acknowledgement

The author would like to acknowledge the support, assistance and guidance given by his PhD supervisor through constructive criticisms and suggestion in the conduct of the research, and also to his co-supervisor. The authors are also grateful to the previous literature research that has been made in any anonymous journal arbitrators related to municipal service delivery and citizen satisfaction. The authors also show their indebtedness to Office for Research, Innovation, Commercialization and Consultancy Management (ORICC) UTHM, Batu Pahat, Johor, Malaysia.

Reference

1. Aagesen, G. (2012). *Multi-channel Provisioning of Public Services* (Vol. 7). Retrieved from <http://brage.bibsys.no/xmlui/handle/11250/252859>
2. Abe, T., Monisola, O. J., & State, E. (2014). Citizen Participation and Service Delivery at the Local Government Level: A Case of Ise/Orun Local Government in Ekiti State, Nigeria. *Journal of Law, Policy and Globalization*, 27(c), 102–110. Retrieved from <http://www.iiste.org/Journals/index.php/JLPG/article/view/14360>
3. Abid, A. (2004). Information literacy for lifelong learning World Library and Information Congress. In *70th IFLA General Conference and Council*. Retrieved from <http://www.ifla.org/IV/ifla70/papers/116e-Abid.pdf> (accessed 18 March 2006)
4. Adeyemi, O. (2013). Local Government and the Challenges of Service Delivery: the Nigeria Experience. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 15(7), 84–98.
5. Agba, M. S., Akwara, A. F., & Idu, A. (2013). Local Government and Social Service Delivery in Nigeria: A Content Analysis. *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies*, 2(2), 455–462. <http://doi.org/10.5901/ajis.2013.v2n2p455>
6. Aijaz, R. (2007). *Challenges for Urban Local Governments in India*. Retrieved from <http://lse.ac.uk/collections/asiaResearchCentre/pdf/WorkingPaper/ARCWorkingPaper19RumiAijaz2007.pdf>

7. Aliyu, A. A., & Abdu, A. A. (2015). Ethno-Religious Violence and Neighbourhood Facilities Provision : Evidence From Jos , Nigeria, *5*(14), 10–26.
8. Almarshad, S. O. (2011). The Impact of Good Governance and Decentralization Reforms on the Effectiveness of Local Authorities: The Case of Saudi Municipalities. Saudi Arabia: University of Connecticut.
9. Almarshad, S. O. (2015). Municipal Awareness and Citizen Satisfaction : The Case of Northern Borders in Saudi Arabia. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, *5*(2), 94–101.
10. Amin, M., & Isa, Z. (2008). An examination of the relationship between service quality perception and customer satisfaction. *Faculty of Science and Technology, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, Bangi, Malaysia*, *1*(3), 191–209. <http://doi.org/10.1108/17538390810901131>
11. Andrews, R., Boyne, G. A., Law, J., & Walker, R. M. (2005). External constraints on local service standards: The case of comprehensive performance assessment in english local government. *Public Administration*, *83*(3), 639–656. <http://doi.org/10.1111/j.0033-3298.2005.00466.x>
12. Antuono, L., Meeks, C., Miller, M. K., & Watchou, J. R. (2006). *Evaluating NGO Service Delivery in South Asia : Lessons for Afghanistan*. PA 860, Workshop in Public Affairs, International Issues.
13. Bache, I. (2013). Measuring quality of life for public policy: an idea whose time has come? Agenda-setting dynamics in the European Union. *Journal of European Public Policy*, *20*(1), 21–38.
14. Barnes, M. (University of B. (1999). Users as citizens: collective action and the local governance of welfare. *Social Policy and Administration*, *33*(1), 73–90. <http://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9515.00132>
15. Blaug, R., Horner, L., & Lekhi, R. (2006). *Public Value , Citizen Expectations and User Commitment - A Literature Review*. The Work Foudation. Retrieved from www.theworkfoundation.com
16. Borins, S. (2012). Innovation in business and government: Looking forward, Canberra, The Australian National University.
17. Callahan, K. (2002). The utilization and effectiveness of citizen advisory committees in the budget process of local governments. *Journal of Public Budgeting, Accounting and Financial Management.*, *14*(2), 295–319.
18. Darison, A.-H. B. (2011). *Enhancing local government revenue mobilization through the use of information communication technology: a case-study of Accra Metropolitan Assembly*.

19. Dewulf, G, and van Meel, J. (2002). User participation and role of information and communication technology, *Diamond. Journal of Corporate Real Estate*, 4(2), 237–247.
20. Ebdon, C. (2002). Beyond the public hearing: citizen participation in the local government budget, process. *Journal of Public Budgeting, Accountability and Financial Management.*, 14(2), 273–294.
21. Filipe, Sa. Álvaro, Rocha. Joaquim, Gonçalves. Manuel, P. C. (2016). Model for the quality of local government online services. *Telematics and Informatics*, 0691(05), 1–10. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.crv.2005.08.004>
22. Group, T. W. B. (2011). *Information is Power*. [Http://go.worldbank.org/IP9RIVSTYO](http://go.worldbank.org/IP9RIVSTYO). Cite visited Aug. 5, 2011.
23. Hanif, Muzammil. and Sehrish, H. A. R. (2010). Factors Affecting Customer Satisfaction. *International Resource Journal of Finance and Economics*, 60(60), 44–52.
24. Hilgers, D., & Ihl, C. (2010). Citizensourcing: Applying the Concept of Open Innovation to the Public Sector. *The International Journal of Public Participation*, 4(1), 67–88.
25. Ireland, C. S. G. (2004). *Delivering Value for People Service Indicators in Local Authorities*.
26. Jusoh, H. (2009). The Role of Efficient Urban Governance in Managing Kuala Lumpur City-Region Development. *Asian Social Science*, 5(8), 14–32.
27. Kaliannan, A., Puteh, F., & Dorasamy, M. (2014). Measuring service quality in malaysian local government: the SERVQUAL approach. In *Knowledge Management International Conference (KMICe)* (Vol. 8, p. 15). <http://doi.org/10.1108/09513559510103157>
28. Kernaghan, K. (2015). Serving seniors: Innovation and public sector service delivery. *Innovation Journal*, 20(2), 1–18.
29. Khalid, S. A. (2010). Improving the Service Delivery : A case Study of Local Authority in Malaysia. *Global Business Review*, 11(1), 65–77. <http://doi.org/10.1177/097215090901100104>
30. Kugonza, S., & Mukobi, R. (2015). Public participation in services delivery projects in Buikwe District Local Government Uganda. *Commonwealth Journal of Local Governance*, 18(4846), 127–147.
31. Lind, H., & Muyingo, H. (2012). Building maintenance strategies: planning under uncertainty. *Property Management*, 30(1), 14–28. <http://doi.org/10.1108/02637471211198152>

32. Mansor, N., & Razali, C. H. C. M. (2010). Customers ' Satisfaction towards Counter Service of Local Authority in Terengganu , Malaysia. *Asian Social Science*, 6(8), 197–208.
33. Mccann, Elizabeth.(University of Wisconsin) & Shannon, S. (School of N. R. and E. U. of M.), Donna, E. (School of N. R. and E. U. of M., & Young, R. D. (School of N. R. and E. U. of M. (1997). Environmental Awareness , Economic Orientation , and Farming Practices : A Comparison of Organic and Conventional Farmers. *Environmental Management*, 21(5), 747–758.
34. Milinthajinda, P. (1999). *Environmental Awareness of Municipality Members in Phetchaburi Province. Thesis, , Bangkok. Kasetsart University.*
35. Mishler, W., & Rose, I. (2001). What are the origins of political trust? Testing institutional and cultural theories in post-communist societies. *Comparative Political Studies*, 34(1), 30–62.
36. Mohamed Osman, M., Izzati Bakri, N. M., Bachok Mansor Ibrahim, S., & Zin Mohamed, M. (2015). Assessing social welfare department service delivery system towards vulnerable and disadvantages group in Malaysia. A case study of Perak. *Procedia Environmental Sciences*, 28(28), 418–426. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.proenv.2015.07.051>
37. Mohammad Anwer Anwer Vatcharaporn Esichaikul Mariam Rehman Maria Anjum. (2016). E-government services evaluation from citizen satisfaction perspective. *Transforming Government: People, Process and Policy*, 10(1), 139–167. <http://doi.org/10.1108/TG-03-2015-0017>
38. Mokhlis, S. (2011). Municipal Service Quality and Citizen Satisfaction in Southern Thailand. *Journal of Public Administration and Governance*, 1(1), 122–137. <http://doi.org/10.5296/jpag.v1i1.717>
39. Newton, K. (2001). Trust, social capital, civil society, and democracy. *International Political Science Review*, 22(2), 201–214.
40. Ofoeze, H. G. A. (2003). Local government and development administration: Issues and cases. In *Development Administration in Nigeria: Issues and Strategies*, edited by Okereke, O. O. P. *WillyRose & Appleseed Publishing Coy.*, 115–129.
41. Putnam, R. (1993). *Making Democracy Work: Civic Traditions in Modern Italy*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
42. Reynolds, P., Mangan, J., Wyld, J., Heath, G., Wilson, B., Bower, P., ... Bower, P. (2011). Property Management Emerald Article : Local authority property management and the maintenance of heritage Local authority property management and the maintenance of heritage.

43. Rozilah Kasim, Musa Alkali Abubakar, Bala, I. (2011). ASESMENT OF SERVICE USER'S EXPERIENCE ON THE FACILITIES PROVISION AT UTHM STUDENTS' RESIDENTIAL COLLEGES., 1–12.
44. Sajid, R. (2013). *Measuring Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty In relation to Online Shopping in Denmark* Author : Sajid Rafique. Aarhus School of Business, University of Aarhus.
45. Samsudin, S., Haron, S., & Bakar, A. N. (2012). Operational Issues in Malaysian Local Authority: Value of Intermediaries Services toward Client Satisfaction. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 68(1), 844–854. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.12.271>
46. Sandford, B. M. (2016). *Local government : alternative models of service delivery*.
47. Sayers, R. (2006). *Awareness-Raising*.
48. Shafie, F. (2013). Fm Desk : User Complaint System As an Fm Approach for Facilities Management Services in Uthm, (May).
49. Siddiquee, N. A. (2006). Public management reform in Malaysia: Recent initiatives and experiences. *International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 19(4), 339–358. <http://doi.org/10.1108/09513550610669185>
50. Stoner-Weiss, K. (1997). *Local Heroes: The Political Economy of Russian Regional Governance*. Princeton, New Jersey: Princeton University Press.
51. Subhan, M., Ghani, A. B. A., & Joarder, M. H. R. (2014). Urban community willingness to pay for improved solid waste management in malaysian municipality: A choice modeling approach. *Asian Social Science*, 10(18), 122–136. <http://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v10n18p122>
52. Sureshchandar, G. S., & Chandreskharan, R. N. (2002). The relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction: a factor specific approach. *Journal of Services Marketing*, 16(4), 363–379.
53. Unegbu, V. E. (2013). Perceived Effect of Local Government Knowledge of Citizens Awareness of Local Government Income on its Utilization in Nigeria. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review(Oman Chapter)*, 2(10), 40–50. <http://doi.org/10.12816/0002332>
54. UNESCO. (2006). *UNESCO Information Literacy Bibliography*. Retrieved from http://www.infolit.org/International_Colloquium/UNESCO_bibliography.
55. Wang, I.-M., & Shieh, C.-J. (2006). The relationship between service quality and customer satisfaction: the example of CJCUC library. *Journal of Information and Optimization Sciences*, 27(1), 193–209. <http://doi.org/10.1080/02522667.2006.10699686>
56. Wihlman, T. (2014). *Innovation in Municipal Welfare Services*.

57. Zamzami, Y. (U. al Q. U. (2004). Neighborhood centers in Saudi society and realistic experience futuristic look. *Mecca: Publications Umm Al Qura University*, 12(2), 153–167.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Social Sciences Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).